

Philodromus otjimbombe (Araneae: Philodromidae), a Namibian species newly recorded and widespread in western South Africa

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INTRODUCTION

The Philodromidae remains very poorly studied in the Afrotropical Region, with only *Tibellus* Simon, 1875 having been revised to date (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994). Most of the described species of the other genera are poorly studied taxonomically and identification relies on outdated descriptions and generally poor illustrations, which is challenging. Currently, 34 species in six genera have been recorded from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022), although many more undescribed species have been distinguished but await description.

As part of a survey of the Succulent Karoo and Desert biomes along the western interior of the Northern Cape, South Africa, five degree-square grids were sampled in summer (January 2021) using a standardized sampling protocol, with the protocol repeated during winter (June–July 2021) in the Richtersveld National Park only (Haddad *et al.*, 2025). Philodromidae was one of the dominant groups of foliage-dwelling spiders sampled at all five sites, with one particular species particularly widespread.

As few philodromid species have been reported from western South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022), identifying this material to species level proved very challenging. Although Simon (1910) described three philodromid species from the Namaqualand Region (Haddad & Marusik, 2019), none were illustrated and only *Tibellus australis* (Simon, 1910) has been subsequently redescribed (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994); *Philodromus vulpio* Simon, 1910 and *Thanatus namaquensis* Simon, 1910 still cannot be reliably identified. After studying numerous papers by Reginald Lawrence on the arachnid fauna of Namibia, it is clear that the dominant foliage-dwelling philodromid from western South Africa had an epigynal morphology consistent with *Philodromus otjimbombe* Lawrence, 1927, described from Otjimbombe at the Kunene River in northern Namibia (Lawrence, 1927).

In this paper, *P. otjimbombe* is illustrated, new records of the species from South Africa are presented, as well as a preliminary phylogeny of South African Philodromidae based on cytochrome oxidase subunit I (COI) sequences, including several specimens of *O. otjimbombe* collected in western South Africa.

Philodromus otjimbombe Lawrence, 1927

Figures 1–13

General habitus of female as in Figs 1–3, of male as in Figs 4–6; small spiders, 2.24–3.66 mm in total length, with creamy-yellow to yellow-brown carapace with broad dark brown stripes laterally and broad white V-shaped marking behind posterior eye row; abdomen white to creamy-brown dorsally and ventrally, with light brown mottling and dark brown heart mark, oblique lateral markings near midpoint, and paired mediolateral chevron markings in posterior half. Legs same colour as carapace, all segments with faint bands, spine bases with black spots; legs relatively longer in males than females.

These two spiders resemble *Philodromus otjimbombe*. The photographs were taken by Cecile Roux in the Namakwa District Municipality, Northern Cape (-28.62, 19.50 and -30.11, 17.59). It was exported on 24 September 2025 from <https://www.innaturalist.org>.

Epigyne as in Figs 7–10; atrium with oblique sclerotized atrial margins, somewhat variable in shape, diverging posteriorly; spermathecae round, touching medially, located posteriorly in epigyne. Male palp as in Figs 11–13; ventral RTA shorter than dorsal RTA in lateral view, dorsal RTA slender, with disto-retrolaterally directed tip; tegulum oval, sperm duct with multiple loops; embolus originating at ca. 10 o'clock, curving around distal margin of tegulum, tip at ca. 1 o'clock.

FIGURES 1–13. *Philodromus otjimbombe*, female (1–3, 7–10) and male (4–6, 11–13). 1–6. Dorsal habitus, showing variation in markings; 7–10. Epigynes, ventral view, showing variation in shape of atrial margins; 11, 12. Palp, ventral view; 13. Palp, retrolateral view. Credits: 1–6, 8–13. Charles Haddad; 7. From Law-

Material examined: SOUTH AFRICA: Northern Cape: Calvinia, Akkerendam Nature Reserve, 31°26.408'S, 19°46.651'E, 1060 m a.s.l., 16.I.2021, leg. C. Haddad, R. Booysen & A. Stander (beating shrubs, open plain), 1♂ 1♀ (NCA 2021/880); Calvinia, Donkieshoek Guest House, 31°27.475'S, 19°47.518'E, 995 m a.s.l., 18.I.2021, leg. C. Haddad & R. Booysen (hand collecting, in house and garden), 1♂ 1♀ (NCA 2021/111); Meerkat National Park, Jaskloof, riparian woodland, 30°46.266'S, 21°14.982'E, 1135 m a.s.l., 1.IV.2025, leg. U.F.S. Entomology students (beating shrubs), 3♂ 1♀ (NMBA 19762); Same locality, koppie plateau, 30°46.198'S, 21°14.804'E, 1210 m a.s.l., 31.III.2025, leg. C. Haddad, R. Booysen & M. Vickers (hand collecting), 1♂ 1♀ (NMBA 19754); Same locality, open plain grassland/thicket, 30°45.935'S, 21°16.345'E, 1120 m a.s.l., 30.III.2025, leg. U.F.S. Entomology students (sweeping grasses), 5♂ 1♀ (NMBA 19802); Same locality, open plain grassland/thicket, 30°45.935'S, 21°16.345'E, 1120 m a.s.l., 30.III.2025, leg. U.F.S. Entomology students (beating shrubs), 2♂ 2♀ (NMBA 19814); Namaqua National Park, Koeroebees, 30°08.683'S, 17°42.177'E, 240 m a.s.l., 14.I.2021,

leg. C. Haddad, R. Booysen, R. Christiaan & A. Stander (leaf litter, dry river bed), 1♀ (NCA 2021/723); Near Nigramoep, Skaaprivier Canyon, 29°33.130'S, 17°39.135'E, 690 m a.s.l., 10.I.2021, leg. C. Haddad, R. Booysen, R. Christiaan & A. Stander (beating shrubs, river bed), 1♂ 6♀ (NCA 2021/513); Nigramoep Slow Living Guest Farm, 29°31.869'S, 17°35.150'E, 745 m a.s.l., 9.I.2021, leg. C. Haddad, R. Booysen, R. Christiaan & A. Stander (beating short shrubs, open plain), 1♂ 1♀ (NCA 2021/609); Richtersveld National Park, SE of Akkedis Pass, 28°11.123'S, 17°02.543'E, 535 m a.s.l., 7.VII.2021, leg. C. Haddad, R. Booysen & M. Vickers (beating short shrubs, dry river bed), 2♀ (NCA 2021/384); Same locality, Sendelingsdrif, Research Accommodation, 28°07.122'S, 16°53.480'E, 40 m a.s.l., 9.VII.2021, leg. C. Haddad & R. Booysen (hand collecting, at night on rocky outcrop), 1♂ (NCA 2021/186). Western Cape: Laingsburg district, Wagendrift Lodge, 33°22.861'S, 20°56.910'E, 520 m a.s.l., 22.I.2021, leg. C. Haddad, R. Booysen & A. Stander (hand collecting, under rocks in veld), 1♀ (NCA 2021/132).

DNA Barcodes: SPIZA579-21; SPIZA673-21; SPIZA674-21; SPIZA700-21; SPIZA826-21; SPIZA892-21; SPIZA893-21. Despite the slight variation in the shape of the epigynal ridges and dorsal RTA between the specimens sequenced (Figs 7–13), the genetic distance between them was less than 1% (Fig. 14), indicating that all these specimens are conspecific. In this analysis, specimens of many of the philodromid genera formed monophyletic groups (*Halodromus*, *Thanatus* and *Hirriusa*), although some others (*Tibellus*, *Gephyrota* and *Suemus*) were unresolved due to the low number of terminals or may be polyphyletic as currently composed (*Philodromus*).

FIGURE 14. Phylogenetic analysis of South African Philodromidae based on cytochrome oxidase subunit I (COI) sequences, which were aligned using Muscle (Edgar 2004), with 200 bp sequence overlap. *Philodromus otjimbumbe* is marked in the orange rectangle and *Moggridgea* sp. (Migidae) was used as the out-group to root the tree.

Distribution: Widespread in western South Africa but in Namibia only recorded from the type locality in the north of the country (Fig. 15); it is thus likely widespread throughout Namibia too.

FIGURE 15. Distribution of *Philodromus otjimbube* in South Africa (white circles) and Namibia (star, type locality). Map produced on simplemappr.net.

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